

COMPARISON OF THE LOAD-SHARING CHARACTERISTICS BETWEEN PEDICLE-BASED COMPOSITE AND RIGID ROD DEVICES

K. Kang¹, H. Chun¹, H. Hong¹

¹School of Mechanical Engineering, Yonsei University, Seoul, Korea,

* Corresponding author (hjchun@yonsei.ac.kr)

Keywords: *Finite element analysis, Pedicle screw, Woven Composite Rod*

1. Introduction

Adjacent segment degeneration (ASD) has been reported as the one of late serious complication after spinal fusion surgery [1-3]. Presumably, the immediate rigidity produced by instrumentation causes more stress leading to accelerated degeneration at adjacent levels [2]. Many previous studies have been corroborated a trend toward earlier development of ASD with instrumentation as well. In contrast, posterior dynamic stabilization (PDS) has been used to overcome the adjacent segment degeneration, one of the serious complications after lumbar fusion. Non-fusion technologies have been developed with the goal of reducing the incidence of arthrodesis-related morbidity. Implant types include total disc replacements, prosthetic nuclear implants and posterior dynamic stabilization devices. Although implants offer some theoretical advantages over fusion, new potential problems such as mechanical failure, device migration, same level degeneration and implant subsidence are associated with new technologies. Furthermore, the efficacy of non-fusion implants in the prevention of adjacent level degeneration was not yet proved. The popularity of non-fusion implants is based more on the lack of satisfaction with conventional spinal fusion rather than their proved superiority. In addition, implants failure (17% of 24 patients) after a 2-years follow-up was found in one study [4]. The stress concentration was suspected to be the main cause of screw breakage [5]. Screw breakage can easily occur in PDS system, surgical technique without cage. However composite material has a good fatigue-failure characteristic. Thus it is appropriate for PDS material. Therefore, in this study, comparison of the biomechanical property of woven composite rod (WCR) with rigid-rod lumbar fusion was evaluated.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Intact Model

A three-dimensional (3D) nonlinear FE model of the lumbar spine that consisted of four lumbar vertebrae, three intervertebral discs, and associated spinal ligaments was developed. Geometrical details of the human lumbar spine (L2-L5) were obtained from high-resolution computed tomography (CT) images of a 46-year-old male subject who had no spinal deformities. Digital CT data were imported to a software program (Mimics; Materialise Inc., Leuven, Belgium) that was used to generate the 3-dimensional geometrical surface of the lumbar spine. Exported IGES files from the Mimics software were input into Unigraphics NX 3.0 (Siemens PLM Software, Torrance, CA) to form solid models for each vertebral segment. The solid model was then imported into Hypermesh 8.0 (Altair Engineering, Inc., Troy, MI) to generate FE meshes. The FE method was analyzed with commercially available software (ABAQUS 6.6-1; Hibbitt, Karlsson and Sorenson, Inc., Providence, RI).

Three-dimensional homogenous and transversely isotropic solid elements were used to model the cortical and cancellous cores, the posterior bony parts of the vertebrae. The anterior longitudinal ligament, posterior longitudinal ligament, intertransverse ligament, ligament flavum, capsular ligament, interspinous ligament, and supraspinous ligament were modeled using tension-only truss elements

2.2 Material properties

Material properties were selected based on various literature sources (Table.1.)[6]. The cortical and cancellous regions of the vertebrae were modeled independently. Differentiation between cortical and

trabecular bone in the posterior region was difficult to delineate; therefore, the posterior elements were all assigned a single set of material properties.

Table.1. Material properties in the present FE models.

Component	Young's modulus (MPa)	Cross-section (mm^2)	Poisson's ratio
Cortical bone	$E_x = 11300$ $E_y = 11300$ $E_z = 22000$ $G_x = 3800$ $G_y = 5400$ $G_z = 5400$		$\nu_{xy} = 0.484$ $\nu_{xz} = 0.203$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.203$
Cancellous bone	$E_x = 140$ $E_y = 140$ $E_z = 200$ $G_x = 48.3$ $G_y = 48.3$ $G_z = 48.3$		$\nu_{xy} = 0.45$ $\nu_{xz} = 0.315$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.315$
Posterior elements	3500		0.25
Disc			
Nucleus pulposus	1.0		0.4999
Annulus (ground substance)	4.2		0.45
Annulus fiber	358 – 550		0.30
Cartilaginous endplate	24.0		0.40
Ligaments			
Anterior longitudinal	7.8(<12%) 20(>12%)	63.7	
Posterior longitudinal	10(<11%) 20(>11%)	20.0	
Ligamentum flavum	15(<6.2%) 19.5(>6.2%)	40.0	
Capsular	7.5(<25%) 32.9(>25%)	30.0	
Interspinous	10(<14%) 11.6(>14%)	40.0	

Supraspinous	8.0 (<20%) 15(>20%)	30.0	
Intertransverse	10(<18%) 58.7(>18%)	1.8	
Fusion mass	3500		0.25
Pedicle screws, rod (Ti6Al4V)	110000		0.3

The annulus fibrosus was modeled as a composite of a solid matrix with embedded fibers (via the REBAR parameter) in concentric rings surrounding a nucleus pulposus, which was considered to be an incompressible inviscid fluid. Element members with hybrid formulation (C3D8H) combined with low elastic modulus and large Poisson ratio definitions were applied to simulate the nucleus pulposus. Eight-node brick elements were employed to model the matrix of the ground substance. Each of four concentric rings of ground substance contained two evenly spaced layers of annulus fibers oriented at $\pm 30^\circ$ to horizontal. The reinforcement structure annulus fibers were represented by truss elements with modified tension-only elasticity. In the radial direction, four double cross-linked fiber layers were defined, and those fibers were bounded by the annulus ground substance and both endplates. In addition, these fibers had proportionally decreased elastic strength from the outermost (550 MPa) to the innermost (358 MPa) layer [7].

The articulating facet joint surfaces were modeled using surface-to-surface contact elements in combination with the penalty algorithm with normal contact stiffness of 200 N/mm and a friction coefficient of zero. The thickness of the cartilage layer of the facet joint was assumed to be 0.2 mm. The initial gap between the cartilage layers was assumed to be 0.5 mm. The cartilage was assumed to be isotropic, linear elastic with a Young's modulus of 35 MPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.4 [8]. Spinal ligaments were represented with nonlinear material properties. Naturally changing ligament stiffness (initially low stiffness at low strains, followed by increasing stiffness at higher strains) was simulated through a "hypoelastic" material designation (Table 1). Three-dimensional truss elements were used to simulate ligaments, which were active only in tension.

2.3 Implanted Model

The implanted models were constructed after modifying the intact model to simulate post-operative changes with these kinds of pedicle screw systems: one kind of WCR devices and a conventional rigid fixation system (Table.2). Since our models were designed to simulate the biomechanical behavior after healing, the bone-implant interface behavior was accomplished via the ‘tie’ contact condition, which enables the screw threads and vertebrae to be bonded together permanently by full constraint (Fig.1) .

Fig.1. Implanted model current study.

Table.2. Material properties and design specification of longitudinal rod.

Implant Type	Diameter	Design	Elastic Modulus (Gpa)
Woven composite (Carbon/Epoxy)	5mm	Cylindrical	64
Ti -alloy	5mm	Cylindrical	114

To validate the model, the same loading conditions used in Yamamoto et al’s study were applied [9]. Therefore, 10 Nm flexion, 10 Nm extension 10Nm torsion, and 10 Nm lateral bending moment under the 150 N preload were imposed on the L2 vertebral body, respectively. To reach 10 Nm moments, the five load steps were applied to models.

2.4 Loading and Boundary Conditions.

The loading condition was the hybrid testing protocol, which was implemented during the flexibility testing of the FE models as described by Goel et al [10] for the study of adjacent level biomechanics. The follower load technique was used to simulate the vector sum of trunk muscle co-activation by using a single internal force vector that acts tangent to the curvature of the spine passing through each segmental center of rotation. This “follower” path acts tangent to the curvature of the spine, thus mimicking the physiologic compressive loads on the lumbar spine seen in vivo. The 400 N compressive follower loads was simulated at each motion segment in the model by a pair of 2-node thermo-isotropic truss elements.

Fig.2. Lateral view of the finite element model showing follower load trusses at each level.

3 Results

The intact *L3-L5* model was validated in our laboratory, as reported in our prior publications [2-3]. The increase of stress in the disc corresponding level was compared among the rigid fixation, the WCR and intact model. The rigid fixation had greater increase of stress in the disc at the *L3-L4* segment in flexion, extension, torsion and lateral bending than the fusion WCR model. The WCR demonstrated less increase of stress in the disc at the *L3-L4* segment than the rigid fixation, but greater increase was inspected in the intact model (Fig.3).

Fig.3. The comparison of the percent change of stress of the intervertebral disc at each corresponding segment in the two models.

Fig.4. The comparison of the range of motion at each corresponding segment in three models (the intact vs. the WCR vs. the rigid fixation).

Under flexion moment, the largest difference of motion at the L2–3 segment (proximal adjacent segment) was observed between the rigid fixation model and the intact model (7.2° vs. 5.2°), and the relatively distal adjacent segment (L4–L5 segment) was less influenced by fusion. In the WCR model, there was less increased motion (5.4°) at the proximal adjacent segment (L2–3), compared to the rigid fixation model (7.2°). The distal adjacent segment was less affected depending on the instrumentation in flexion moment than the proximal adjacent segment (Fig. 4) L3–4 fusion also produced increased motion at both adjacent segments under extension moment. Changes of adjacent segment motion in the rigid fixation model became more pronounced than in the WCR model. Proximal adjacent segment in the rigid fixation model had 4.6° of ROM while the corresponding segment in the WCR model had 3.8° of ROM. Furthermore,

compared to flexion moment, difference of ROM in distal adjacent segments (L4–5) (1.5°) between rigid fixation and WCR model had similar to the proximal adjacent segment (L2–3) (1.2°). Similar patterns of changes of motion to flexion and extension moment were also shown under torsion (axial rotation) and lateral bending moment. L3–4 fusion (rigid fixation and WCR model) caused increased motion at both adjacent segments, and the changes became more prominent in the rigid fixation model than in the WCR model (Fig.4)

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, the ROM and disc stress of the WCR model were similar to those of the intact spine, and the stress on the adjacent level was decreased in comparison with a fused spine. These results suggest that the use of PDS devices can restore functionality similar to that of the intact spine and suggest that stiffness should be an important parameter in the design of dynamic stabilization devices. Although an FE model of the lumbar spine was used to verify the usefulness of the PDS device and to investigate its design parameters, this verified FE model with tuned parameter values can also be used for designing other types of spinal implants.

References

- [1] P. Park, H. Garton and V. Gala "Adjacent segment disease after lumbar or lumbosacral fusion: review of the literature". *Spine*, Vol. 29, pp 1938-4, 2004.
- [2] K. Kang, H. Chun and J. Son "The Change of Biomechanical Milieu after Removal of Instrumentation in Lumbar Arthrodesis Stiffness of Fusion Mass: Finite Element Analysis". *The KSME annual fall conference*, Jeju, Vol. 1 pp. 664-667, 2008.
- [3] H. Kim, H. Chun and K. Kang "A validated finite element analysis of nerve root stress in degenerative lumbar scoliosis", *Med Biol Eng Comput*, Vol. 47, pp. 599–605, 2009.
- [4]] K. Schnake, S. Schaeren and B. Jeanneret "Dynamic stabilization in addition to decompression for lumbar spinal stenosis with degenerative spondylolisthesis", *Spine*, Vol. 31, pp. 442–449, 2006
- [5] J. Cotler and A. Star "Complications of spine fusions" 1st Edition, Springer-Verlag, 1990.
- [6] V. Goel, Y. Kim and T. Lim, "An analytical investigation of the mechanics of spinal instrumentation". *Spine* Vol. 13, pp. 1003-1011, 1988.

- [7] A. Polikeit, S. Ferguson and L. Nolte, “Factors influencing stresses in the lumbar spine after the insertion of intervertebral cages: finite element analysis”. *European Spine Journal*, Vol.12, pp. 413-420, 2003.
- [8] H. Schmidt, F. Galbusera and A. Rohlmann, “Effect of multilevel lumbar disc arthroplasty on spine kinematics and facet joint loads in flexion and extension: a finite element analysis”. *European Spine Journal* , Accepted, 2010.
- [9] I. Yamamoto, M. Panjabi and T. Crisco “Three-dimensional movements of the whole lumbar spine and lumbosacral joint” *Spine* Vol. 14, pp. 1256–1260, 1989.
- [10] V. Goel, J. Grauer and T. Patel “Effects of charité artificial disc on the implanted and adjacent spinal segments mechanics using a hybrid testing protocol”. *Spine* Vol. 30, pp. 2755-2764, 2005.